

For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

Improved Line-of-Sight Guidance Law for Path Following of Autonomous Underwater Vehicle with Compensation of Drift and Lift Forces

Lazar Ašanin, Luka Martinović, *Member, IEEE*, Žarko Zečević, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—This paper presents an improved line-of-sight guidance law for robust path following of autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) subjected to drift and lift forces induced by environmental disturbances. The proposed method compensates the sideslip angle and angle of attack by integrating a Kalman-like observer into the LOS framework, enabling accurate and fast estimation of these parameters. By leveraging these estimates, the AUV achieves convergence to the desired path while mitigating path following errors caused by drift and lift forces. Comprehensive simulation studies validate the effectiveness of the guidance law.

Index Terms—AUV, Guidance, Path Following, Line-of-Sight (LOS), 3D, Sideslip, Angle of Attack

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have become indispensable tools in scientific, commercial, and military applications, including environmental monitoring [1], seabed mapping [2], mine detection [3], and pipeline inspection [4]. Effective path following capability is crucial for AUVs to perform these tasks with precision and safety in dynamic underwater environments. The goal of path following task is to ensure adherence to a predefined path without imposing temporal constraints [5], [6]. This process entails the independent definition of the geometric path and the dynamic assignment, prioritizing spatial convergence as the primary objective while treating dynamic considerations as secondary [7], [8]. However, AUVs face challenges such as unknown environmental disturbances (e.g. ocean currents), coupled nonlinear dynamics, and sideslip effects, all of which can degrade path following performance [3].

The line-of-sight (LOS) guidance law is widely utilized for path following tasks in marine surface vessels due to its simplicity in transforming position errors into heading adjustments [5], [9]–[11]. LOS guidance for AUVs simplifies path following by decomposing it into horizontal-plane tracking and one-dimensional depth control [12], [13]. While this decoupled approach offers simplicity, it becomes increasingly challenging when considering the greater degrees of

freedom (DOFs) and coupled dynamics inherent in 3D space. Following the guidance principles outlined in [8], several studies have extended LOS guidance to 3D path following through coupled horizontal-vertical plane coordination [7], [14]–[16]. However, these implementations retain the traditional LOS formulation without explicit compensation for sideslip angle and angle of attack caused by ocean currents. This omission proves problematic as current-induced drift and lift forces create a discrepancy between the AUV's intended heading/pitch and its actual direction of motion, manifesting as persistent tracking errors, that necessitate computationally intensive corrective actions in the dynamics control layer [7], [17].

To address these challenges, several guidance methods have been developed that incorporate real-time estimation of the sideslip and angle of attack within the guidance law. Notably, nonlinear integral LOS (ILOS) guidance in [17] treats the sideslip angle as a constant parameter compensated through an inverse tangent function, but shows limitations for rapidly varying currents [3]. Adaptive 3D LOS (ALOS) methods introduced in [3], [5] improve dynamic response by directly estimating time-varying sideslip angle and angle of attack parameters outside the inverse tangent function, which compensates for the rapid angle change induced by time-varying environmental disturbances. While ALOS effectively handles transient current variations, these methods exhibit convergence overshoot during aggressive maneuvers. To prevent large oscillations, the adaptation gain must be limited, which in turn slows convergence.

In this paper, we present an improved 3D LOS guidance law for the path following of underactuated AUVs, incorporating drift and lift force compensation. To improve performance, we employ an observer to estimate surge, sway, and heave velocities, from which sideslip and angle of attack estimates are subsequently derived. This approach contrasts with existing ILOS and ALOS methods, which directly estimate these angles. As a result, the proposed method achieves faster convergence and superior path following performance, as demonstrated through numerical simulations.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II presents the AUV kinematic model and path following problem formulation. The proposed observer-based LOS guidance law is detailed in Section III. Simulation results are provided in Section IV, followed by concluding remarks in Section V.

*This paper is supported by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060395, Twinning project MONUSEN.

L. Ašanin, L. Martinović and Ž. Zečević are with Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Montenegro, Džordža Vašingtona bb, Podgorica, Montenegro, e-mails: asaninlazarlaix@gmail.com, {lukam, zarkoz}@ucg.ac.me.

Fig. 1: LOS guidance geometry for 3D path following [9].

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) typically employ a 6-degree-of-freedom (DOF) kinematic model, accounting for surge, sway, heave, pitch, yaw, roll. However, slender-body AUVs leverage the metacentric height between their centers of gravity and buoyancy to passively stabilize roll through hydrostatic restoring moments. This allows simplification to a 5-DOF model excluding roll dynamics for 3D path following control [7], [9], [16]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = u \cos(\psi) \cos(\theta) - v \sin(\psi) + w \cos(\psi) \sin(\theta), \\ \dot{y} = u \sin(\psi) \cos(\theta) + v \cos(\psi) + w \sin(\psi) \sin(\theta), \\ \dot{z} = -u \sin(\theta) + w \cos(\theta), \\ \dot{\theta} = q, \\ \dot{\psi} = r / \cos(\theta), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = [x, y, z]^T$ denotes the position of the AUV in an earth-fixed reference frame $\{I\}$, ψ and θ represent the heading and pitch angles, also expressed in $\{I\}$ frame, while u, v, w, q, r denote surge, sway, and heave velocities, as well as the yaw and pitch rates, respectively, in a body-fixed frame $\{B\}$ (see Fig. 1).

The desired path $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_d$ is parameterized as $\mathbf{p}_P(s) = [x_d(s), y_d(s), z_d(s)]^T$ where s represents the path variable. In order to define the model for path following errors, the earth-fixed frame is rotated by an azimuth angle $\psi_p = \text{atan2}(y'_d(s), x'_d(s))$ about the z -axis and an elevation angle $\theta_p = \text{atan2}(-z'_d(s), \sqrt{x_d'^2(s) + y_d'^2(s)})$ about the resulting y -axis, where $x'_d(s) = \partial x_d / \partial s$, $y'_d(s) = \partial y_d / \partial s$ and $z'_d(s) = \partial z_d / \partial s$ [18]. The two corresponding rotation matrices are:

$$\mathbf{R}_{P,z}(\psi_p) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi_p) & -\sin(\psi_p) & 0 \\ \sin(\psi_p) & \cos(\psi_p) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{P,y}(\theta_p) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_p) & 0 & \sin(\theta_p) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta_p) & 0 & \cos(\theta_p) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

This results in:

$$\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{R}_P^T(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_P(s)), \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_P = \mathbf{R}_{P,z}(\psi_p) \mathbf{R}_{P,y}(\theta_p) \quad (5)$$

represents the rotation matrix from $\{I\}$ to $\{P\}$ frame. The components of the error vector $\boldsymbol{\xi} = [x_e, y_e, z_e]^T$ represent the along-track, cross-track, and vertical-track errors, respectively.

Derivation of (4) and substitution of (1) gives the following error dynamics

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \mathbf{S}_P^T \boldsymbol{\xi} + \mathbf{v}_P + \mathbf{R}_P^T \mathbf{R}_I \mathbf{v}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = [u, v, w]^T$, $\mathbf{v}_P = [-u_p, 0, 0]^T$, $\mathbf{R}_I = \mathbf{R}_z(\psi) \mathbf{R}_y(\theta)$ and $\mathbf{S}_P = -\mathbf{S}_P^T$ is the skew-symmetric matrix:

$$\mathbf{S}_P = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\dot{\psi}_p \cos(\theta_p) & \dot{\theta}_p \\ \dot{\psi}_p \cos(\theta_p) & 0 & \dot{\psi}_p \sin(\theta_p) \\ -\dot{\theta}_p & -\dot{\psi}_p \sin(\theta_p) & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

The speed u_p of the virtual reference point is given by

$$u_p = \dot{s} \sqrt{x_d'^2(s) + y_d'^2(s) + z_d'^2(s)}. \quad (8)$$

Influences of ocean currents on the path following are described via the sideslip angle $\beta = \arctan(v/u)$ and the angle of attack $\alpha = \arctan(w/u)$ [3].

The control objective for the path following scenario is to construct the guidance law and path variable update law \dot{s} , that enable the AUV to track the desired reference 3D path $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_d$ (see Fig. 1), thus minimizing the path following errors x_e, y_e and z_e [3].

III. PROPOSED 3D LOS GUIDANCE ALGORITHM

In this section, a novel 3D LOS guidance law based on a Kalman-like observer is proposed to make an AUV follow a specified parameterized path.

First, we introduce the observer to estimate surge, sway and heave velocities based on the dynamics in (6):

$$\dot{\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}_P^T & \mathbf{R}_P^T \mathbf{R}_I \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_P \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\xi} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}), \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}} = [\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^T \hat{\mathbf{v}}^T]^T$ is the estimation of augmented state vector $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = [\boldsymbol{\xi}^T \mathbf{v}^T]^T$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the time-varying gain updated as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{P}} &= \mathbf{A} \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A}^T - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{Q} \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma} &= \mathbf{P} \mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In (10), \mathbf{P} denotes the error covariance matrix, \mathbf{Q} represents the process noise covariance matrix, while \mathbf{R} refers to the measurement noise covariance matrix. Given that process and measurement noise are not considered in this study, \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} can be leveraged to control the convergence rate of the estimator. Furthermore, matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{C} are defined as

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}_P^T & \mathbf{R}_P^T \mathbf{R}_I \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}_{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}(t) = \hat{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}(t)}, \quad \mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{I}_3 \quad \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}]. \quad (11)$$

By obtaining the estimates of surge, sway, and heave velocities, it is possible to compute the corresponding estimated values for the sideslip angle and angle of attack:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\beta} = \arctan(\hat{v}/\hat{u}), \\ \hat{\alpha} = \arctan(\hat{w}/\hat{u}) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

To compensate the influence of drift and lift forces, the desired heading and pitch angle are defined as [5]:

$$\psi_d = \psi_p - \arctan\left(\frac{y_e}{\Delta_\psi}\right) - \hat{\beta}, \quad (13)$$

$$\theta_d = \theta_p + \arctan\left(\frac{z_e}{\Delta_\gamma}\right) + \hat{\alpha}, \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta_\psi > 0$ and $\Delta_\gamma > 0$ are the user-specified lookahead distances.

The virtual input u_p is selected as

$$u_p = U \cos(\psi - \psi_p + \hat{\beta}) \cos(\theta - \theta_p - \hat{\alpha}) + k_1 x_e, \quad (15)$$

where $k_1 > 0$ is a constant gain parameter, $U = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2 + w^2}$ is the resultant speed of the vehicle. Considering (8), the following path variable update law can be derived to stabilize the along-track error:

$$\dot{s} = \frac{U \cos(\psi - \psi_p + \hat{\beta}) \cos(\theta - \theta_p - \hat{\alpha}) + k_1 x_e}{\sqrt{x_d'^2(s) + y_d'^2(s) + z_d'^2(s)}}. \quad (16)$$

The path variable update law (16) and the guidance laws (13) and (14) ensure the convergence of an AUV to the desired path. Notably, the proposed approach is capable of compensating for significant sideslip and angle of attack, as no assumptions are made regarding their magnitudes.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The convergence properties of the proposed LOS method are compared with 3D ALOS guidance law. Two path following scenarios are considered:

- S1 (straight line): $x_d(s)=s, y_d(s)=0.5s, z_d(s)=0.2s,$
- S2 (spiral path): $x_d(s)=50 \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{50}\right), y_d(s)=50 \cos\left(\frac{\pi s}{50}\right), z_d(s)=s.$

The guidance law parameters for both scenarios are set as follows: $\Delta_\psi = 5m, \Delta_\gamma = 5m, \gamma_h = 0.01, \gamma_v = 0.01,$ and the diagonal elements of covariance matrices \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{Q} are set to 10. The vehicle's surge, sway, and heave velocities are maintained at $u = 3m/s, v = 0.6m/s$ and $w = -0.4m/s.$

The simulation results for scenario S1 are illustrated in Figs. 2-6. Specifically, Figs. 2-4 demonstrate that the proposed method achieves significantly faster convergence to the desired straight-line path compared to the ALOS guidance law. As shown in Fig. 5, the along-track, cross-track, and vertical-track errors converge within 10 seconds when using the proposed algorithm, whereas the ALOS guidance law requires 50 seconds to reach steady state. These results are further supported by Fig. 6, which highlights that the proposed algorithm estimates the sideslip and angle of attack significantly faster than the ALOS method.

The simulation results for scenario S2 are presented in Figs. 7-11. Figs. 7-9 illustrate that the proposed guidance law delivers exceptional path following performance along the spiral path. The rapid convergence of path following errors, as shown in Fig. 10, is attributed to the swift and accurate estimation of sideslip and angle of attack, as depicted in Fig. 11.

Fig. 2: S1: 3D Path following - Straight line

Fig. 3: S1: Horizontal-plane path following performance

Fig. 4: S1: Vertical-plane path following performance

Fig. 5: S1: Path following errors

Fig. 6: S1: Comparison of sideslip and angle of attack estimates

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an improved LOS guidance law for robust 3D path following of underactuated AUVs, addressing

Fig. 7: S2: 3D Path following - Spiral

Fig. 8: S2: Horizontal-plane path following performance

Fig. 9: S2: Vertical-plane path following performance

Fig. 10: S2: Path following errors

Fig. 11: S2: Comparison of sideslip and angle-of-attack estimates

challenges posed by environmental disturbances such as drift and lift forces. By integrating an observer into the LOS framework, the guidance law provides real-time estimates

and compensation for sideslip and angle of attack, ensuring accurate path following. Simulation results for both straight-line and curved paths confirm the method's efficacy, with rapid minimization of tracking errors, attributable to the fast estimation of the sideslip and angle of attack.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Bovio, D. Cecchi, and F. Baralli, "Autonomous underwater vehicles for scientific and naval operations," *Annu. Rev. Control*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 117–130, 2006.
- [2] Y. Sato, T. Maki, A. Kume, T. Matsuda, T. Sakamaki, and T. Ura, "Path Replanning Method for an AUV in Natural Hydrothermal Vent Fields: Toward 3D Imaging of a Hydrothermal Chimney," *Mar. Technol. Soc. J.*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 104–114, 2014.
- [3] L. He, Y. Zhang, G. Fan, Y. Liu, X. Wang, and Z. Yuan, "Three-Dimensional Path Following Control of Underactuated AUV Based on Nonlinear Disturbance Observer and Adaptive Line-of-Sight Guidance," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 83 911–83 924, 2024.
- [4] X. Xiang, B. Jouvencel, and O. Parodi, "Coordinated formation control of multiple autonomous underwater vehicles for pipeline inspection," *Int. J. Adv. Robot. Syst.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 75–84, 2010.
- [5] T. I. Fossen and A. P. Aguiar, "A uniform semiglobal exponential stable adaptive line-of-sight (ALOS) guidance law for 3-D path following," *Automatica*, vol. 163, p. 111556, 2024.
- [6] Z. Zecevic, L. Martinovic, L. Asanin, M. Bibuli, R. Ferretti, A. Odetti, S. Aracri, and M. Caccia, "KF-based LOS Guidance Law for Path Following of USV: Experiments and Performance Evaluation," *2024 28th Int. Conf. Inf. Technol. IT 2024*, 2024.
- [7] C. Yu, X. Xiang, L. Lapiere, and Q. Zhang, "Nonlinear guidance and fuzzy control for three-dimensional path following of an underactuated autonomous underwater vehicle," *Ocean Eng.*, vol. 146, pp. 457–467, 2017.
- [8] M. Breivik and T. I. Fossen, "Principles of guidance-based path following in 2D and 3D," in *Proc. 44th IEEE Conf. Decis. Control. Eur. Control Conf. CDC-ECC '05*, 2005, pp. 627–634.
- [9] N. Gu, D. Wang, Z. Peng, J. Wang, and Q. L. Han, "Advances in Line-of-Sight Guidance for Path Following of Autonomous Marine Vehicles: An Overview," *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man, Cybern. Syst.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 12–28, 2023.
- [10] L. Martinovic, Z. Zecevic, M. Bibuli, M. Caccia, and D. Nad, "Adaptive Observer-Based Line-of-Sight Guidance Law for Path Following of Underactuated Unmanned Surface Vehicle with Sideslip Compensation," *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [11] L. Asanin, L. Martinovic, Z. Zecevic, M. Bibuli, R. Ferretti, and M. Caccia, "Improved LOS Guidance Law for Path Following of Underactuated USV with Sideslip Compensation," in *2023 27th Int. Conf. Inf. Technol. IT 2023*, 2023.
- [12] A. M. Lekkas, "Guidance and Path-Planning Systems for Autonomous Vehicles," 2014.
- [13] W. Caharija, K. Y. Pettersen, M. Bibuli, P. Calado, E. Zereik, J. Braga, J. T. Gravdahl, A. J. Sorensen, M. Milovanovic, and G. Bruzzone, "Integral Line-of-Sight Guidance and Control of Underactuated Marine Vehicles: Theory, Simulations, and Experiments," *IEEE Trans. Control Syst. Technol.*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 1623–1642, 2016.
- [14] M. Breivik and T. I. Fossen, "A unified control concept for autonomous underwater vehicles," in *Proc. Am. Control Conf.*, 2006, pp. 4920–4926.
- [15] G. Q. Xia, Y. Yang, and W. G. Zhao, "Path-following in 3D for underactuated AUV in the presence of ocean current," *Proc. - 2013 5th Conf. Meas. Technol. Mechatronics Autom. ICMTMA 2013*, pp. 788–791, 2013.
- [16] X. Xiang, C. Yu, and Q. Zhang, "Robust fuzzy 3D path following for autonomous underwater vehicle subject to uncertainties," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 84, pp. 165–177, 2017.
- [17] X. Yao, X. Wang, X. Jiang, and F. Wang, "Control for 3D path-following of underactuated autonomous underwater vehicle under current disturbance," *Harbin Gongye Daxue Xuebao/Journal Harbin Inst. Technol.*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 37–45, 2019.
- [18] J. Liu, Z. Liu, and J. Yu, "Line-of-sight based three-dimensional path following control for an underactuated robotic dolphin," *Sci. China Inf. Sci.*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2021.